

PHARMACOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE DRUG "SIRIMOL"

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses conditions in which the body's need for biologically active substances such as minerals, vitamins, amino acids, macro and microelements increases. The drug Sirimol is recommended as a drug that fills this need of the body and is used in the form of capsules and syrup.

Relevance. It is known that for admission to higher educational institutions, parents try to arrange their children – future applicants in certain courses in specific disciplines, which imposes a great responsibility on the child [1, 16, 30]. A child with such responsibility tries to prepare day and night, read and write – that is, imposes a great mental load on the body. At the same time, metabolism increases in a young body, which leads to an increase in the body's, and especially the brain's, energy requirements, nutrients, such as amino acids, vitamins, minerals and other biologically active substances [2, 17]. Often, such children have a reduced appetite – they eat little, which leads to metabolic disorders and the child feels tired, sleep disturbance, apathy and a decrease in intellectual and physical performance. Also, there is often a decrease in immunity and a tendency of the child to colds and other diseases [3, 18, 31]. Therefore, the growing body needs support in the form of easily digestible minerals

and vitamins, energy substances and amino acids, biologically active substances [4, 19, 32].

Amino acids, being the main components of protein, serve as the building material of a living organism, they are also necessary for the formation of hormones, neurotransmitters (chemicals involved in the transmission of nerve impulses) and enzymes, are required for the preservation and restoration of muscles, tendons, skin, ligaments, various organs, glands, nails and hair [5, 20]. One of the groups of amino acids, these are essential amino acids that are not synthesized in the body and must come from outside. These include: isoleucine, leucine, lysine, methionine, phenylalanine, threonine, tryptophan and valine [6, 21, 33].

The preparation Sirimol in the form of a capsule contains 27 components, which include amino acids, multivitamins and multiminerals (table). And Sirimol syrup contains 19 components [7, 22, 34].

The purpose of our study was the use of the drug Sirimol in children attending preparatory courses in biology and chemistry and the study of the pharmacological effect of Sirimol on

intellectual abilities – the assimilation of new material by applicants in the subjects [8, 23, 35].

Table. The composition of the drug Sirimol

Active substances	Dose (mg)	Active substances	Dose
L-threonine	4,2	Cyanocobalamin (vit B12)	2,5 mkg
L-valine	6,7	Ascorbic acid (vit C)	40,0 mg
DL-methionine	18,4	Synthetic Retinol concentrate (in powder form) vit A	2500 ME
L-Isoleucine	5,9	Cholecalciferol (vit D)	200 ME
L-leytsin	18,3	Alfa tokoferol asetat (vit E)	7,5 ME
L-fenilalanin	5,0	5-hydroxy anthranilic acid hydrochloride L1	0,2 mg
L- tryptophan	5,0	Potassium iodide	0,1 mg
L-Lysine hydrochloride	25,0	Iron Sulfate	20,5 mg
Thiamine Nitrate (Vit B1)	5,0	Copper sulfate	4,0 mg
Riboflavin(Vit B2)	3,0	Manganese Sulfate	1,4 mg
Pyridoxine Hydrochloride (Vit B6)	1,5	Magnesium Sulfate	7,425 mg
Nicotinamide (Vit PP)	25,0	Zinc sulfate	3,3 mg
Calcium Pantothenate (Vit B5)	5,0	Sodium Selenite	10 mkg
Folic acid (Vit B9)	0,75		

Materials and methods of research. We conducted a questionnaire survey of 100 applicants from the preparatory courses of biology (50) and chemistry (50) before the use of the drug Sirimol, during the administration of the drug (every decade of the month) and after its use (at the end of the month) [9, 24, 36]. Sirimol was prescribed 1 capsule 1 time a day to drink after meals for 1 month. The results were processed by the statistical method [10, 25, 37].

The results of the study. The obtained clinical data showed that after the use of Sirimol, starting from day 3, sleep began to

normalize in applicants (Fig. 1), which in the first decade of observation was 28%, and in the second decade of the study, applicants noted a feeling of improvement and improvement in mental performance (44%), an increase in mood (52%), resumption of desire to learn (85%) [11, 26, 38]. By the end of the course of treatment, applicants noted an improvement in all intellectual indicators (93%), an increase in mental and physical performance (95%). There was also a decrease in the frequency of colds (84%) and other diseases (42%) [12, 27, 39].

Decade-1, Decade-2, Decade-3.

Figure 1. Pharmacological effects of Sirimol

All these phenomena are explained by the fact that the drug Sirimol contains 27 components – these are 8 essential amino acids, such as isoleucine, leucine, lysine, methionine, phenylalanine, threonine, tryptophan, valine, as well as B vitamins (B1, B2, B5, B6, B9, B12), vitamins A, C, D, E – antioxidants and trace elements - iodine, iron, selenium, copper, manganese, magnesium, zinc [13, 28]. Such a complex helps to fill in the missing parts of the metabolism and leads to the restoration of the functions of all organs and systems, and especially of the organ that receives the

highest load – the brain [14, 29]. The noted positive effect of the drug Sirimol, along with other organs, leads to an increase in the intellectual abilities of applicants, an increase in not only mental, but also physical performance – as the applicants themselves note, which took place in our observations [15, 30].

Conclusions. Thus, we believe that with an increase in mental and physical activity, as well as during the period of increasing the body's need for nutrients, energy sources should be recommended the drug Sirimol, which leads to filling all the needs of a growing organism and increasing intellectual ability, especially for applicants.

References:

1. В.В.Горбачёв, В.Н.Горбачёва. Витамины, микро и макроэлементы. Справочник. Москва. Книжный дом. 2002. – 544 с.
2. Самадов, Б. Ш., Мусаева, Д. М., & Дубинина, Н. В. (2019). Сравнительная характеристика и тенденции развития эпидемического процесса гепатита С в Украине и в Узбекистане. Новый день в медицине, (4), 284-290.
3. Дубинина, Н. В., Дубинина, Н. В., Самадов, Б. Ш., Тищенко, И. Ю., & Тищенко, И. Ю. (2020). Перспективы использования лекарственного сырья момордика харанция для создания новых лекарственных средств.

4. Samadov, B. S., Yaremenko, V. D., & Berezniakova, N. L. (2018). Standartization of active pharmaceutical ingredients in combined dosage form.
5. Samadov, B. S. (2022). THE USE OF THE MEDICINAL PLANT MOMORDICA CHARANTIA L IN FOLK MEDICINE. Asian journal of pharmaceutical and biological research, 11(2).
6. Samadov, B. S., Jalilova, F. S., & Jalilov, F. S. (2022). PROSPECTS FOR OBTAINING DOSAGE FORMS BASED ON MOMORDICA CHARANTIAL. Редакційна колегія, 37.
7. Применение Сиримола при интеллектуальной нагрузке. Истамова С., Мусаева Д.М. Сборник материалов II Международной студенческой научно-практической онлайн-конференции "Мир глазами молодых. Студенческие чтения". Курск, 15 мая 2019 года. С.151-153.
8. Samadov, B. S., Jalilova, F. S., & Jalilov, F. S. (2022). COMPOSITION AND TECHNOLOGY OF COLLECTION OF MOMORDICA CHARANTIA L OBTAINED FROM MEDICINAL PLANT RAW MATERIALS. Scientific progress, 3(8), 42-48.
9. Самадов Б. Ш., Жалилова Ф. С., Жалилов Ф. С. ХИМИЧЕСКИЙ СОСТАВ ПЛОДЫ "MOMORDICA CHARANTIA L" ВЫРАЩЕННОГО В УСЛОВИЯХ БУХАРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН. Матеріали ІХ Міжнародної науково-практичної internet-конференції «Сучасні досягнення фармацевтичної технології». Харків, НФаУ. Редакційна колегія. – 2021. – С. 3-7.
10. Б.Ш. Самадов, Ф.С. Жалилова, Ф.С. Жалилов, Н.А. Муродова., Фармакологическая свойства и химический состав лекарственного растительного сырья "Momordica Charantia L". Матеріали ІV Міжнародної науково-практичної конференції. Харків, НФаУ, 2020. С. 426-430.
11. Самадов, Б. Ш., Жалилова, Ф. С., Жалилов, Ф. С., & Муродова, Н. А. (2020). ФАРМАКОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ СВОЙСТВА И ХИМИЧЕСКИЙ СОСТАВ ЛЕКАРСТВЕННОГО РАСТИТЕЛЬНОГО СЫРЬЯ "MOMORDICA CHARANTIA L". Новый день в медицине. Научно-реферативный, духовно-просветительский журнал, 1, 29.
12. Е.А. Докучаева, В. Э. Сяхович, Н. В. Богданова. Общая биохимия: витамины. Практикум. Минск. «ИВЦ Минфина» 2017. 53 с.
13. Самадов, Б. Ш., & Мусаева, Д. М. (2020). Тенденция развития эпидемического процесса гепатита С в Узбекистане. Матеріали ІV Міжнародної науково-практичної конференції. НФаУ, Харьков. Украина, 430-437.
14. Samadov, B. S., & Dubinina, N. V. (2016). Characteristics and trends of epidemic of hepatitis C in Uzbekistan and Ukraine.
15. Самадов, Б. Ш., Жалилов, Ф. С., & Жалилова, Ф. С. (2020). ВЫРАЩИВАНИЕ ЛЕКАРСТВЕННОГО РАСТЕНИЯ «MOMORDICA CHARANTIA L» В УСЛОВИЯХ БУХАРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ. Вестник науки и образования, (21-1 (99)), 92-98.
16. Дубинина, Н. В., Самадов, Б. Ш., Тищенко, И. Ю., Дубініна, Н. В., & Тищенко, І. Ю. (2020). Вирусные гепатиты с парентеральным механизмом передачи: современные подходы к лечению.
17. Иозефович Ольга Витальевна, Рулева А. А., Харит С. М., Муравьева Н. Н. Выбираем витамины // ВСП. 2010. №1.
18. Швець, І. О., Самадов, Б. Ш., Ільїна, Т. В., & Ільїна, Т. В. (2017). Навчальна практика з фармакогнозії-складова частина професійної підготовки провізора.

19. Samadov, B., Sych, I. A., Shpychak, T. V., & Kiz, O. V. (2017). Quantitative determination by potentiometric titration method of active pharmaceutical ingredients in complex dosage form.
20. Самадов, Б. Ш., Жалилов, Ф. С., Жалилова, Ф. С., & Шарипова Э.М. (2021). ХИМИЧЕСКИЙ СОСТАВ ЛЕКАРСТВЕННОГО СЫРЬЯ "МОМОРДИКА CHARANTIA L", ВЫРАЩИВАННОГО В УСЛОВИЯХ БУХАРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН. Вестник науки и образования, (15-1), 106-110.
21. Дубинина, Н. В., Самадов, Б. Ш., & Тищенко, И. Ю. (2021). Создание вакцин для профилактики и лечения ВИЧ.
22. Коденцова В.М. Витамины и минералы как фактор предупреждения дефектов развития плода и осложнений беременности // МС. 2016. №9.
23. Bakhodirjon Sharipovich Samadov. (2022). THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE MEDICINAL PLANT MOMORDICA CHARANTIA L USED IN FOLK MEDICINE. Thematics Journal of Chemistry, 6(1).
24. Samadov, B. S. (2022). ANATOMICAL STRUCTURE OF THE MEDICINAL PLANT MOMORDICA CHARANTIA L. Thematics Journal of Botany, 6(1).
25. Самадов, Б. Ш., Болтаев, М. М., Мелибоева, Ш. Ш., & Жалилов, Ф. С. (2022). ГИПОЛИПИМИДЕМИЧЕСКАЯ АКТИВНОСТЬ СЫРЬЯ ПЛОДЫ МОМОРДИКА ХАРАНЦИЯ (МОМОРДИКА CHARANTIA L). Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research, 2(8), 26-35.
26. Samadov, B. S., Jalilova, F. S., Ziyaeva, D. A., Sharipova, D. S., Ozodova, N. X., & Norova, H. U. & Kudina, OV (2020). Pharmacological properties and chemical composition "Momordica charantia l.
27. Самадов, Б. Ш. (2020). Жалилов Фазлиддин Содикович, Жалилова Феруза Содиковна. ВЫРАЩИВАНИЕ ЛЕКАРСТВЕННОГО РАСТЕНИЯ «МОМОРДИКА CHARANTIA L» В УСЛОВИЯХ БУХАРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ. Вестник науки и образования, (21-1), 99.
28. Samadov, B. S., Jalilova, F. S., & Jalilov, F. S. (2022). COMPOSITION AND TECHNOLOGY OF COLLECTION OF INDIAN POMEGRANATE OBTAINED FROM MEDICINAL PLANT RAW MATERIALS. Редакційна колегія, 40.
29. Samadov, B. S., Jalilova, F. S., & Jalilov, F. S. (2022). ANALYSIS OF THE COMPONENTS OF THE COLLECTION OF MEDICINAL PLANT RAW MATERIALS OF INDIAN POMEGRANATE. Редакційна колегія, 43.
30. Максимов М. Л. и др. Общие вопросы клинической фармакологии и фармакотерапии. – 2020.
31. Samadov, B. S., Jalilova, F. S., & Jalilov, F. S. (2022). PROSPECTS FOR OBTAINING DOSAGE FORMS BASED ON LOCALIZED INDIAN POMEGRANATE. Редакційна колегія, 169.
32. Самадов, Б. Ш., Джалилов, Ф. С., Юлдашева, Д. Х., Джалилова, Ф. С., Болтаев, М. М., & Мелибоева, Ш. Ш. к. (2022). ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ В НАРОДНЫЕ МЕДИЦИНЫ ПЛОДЫ ЛЕКАРСТВЕННОГО РАСТЕНИЯ МОМОРДИКА CHARANTIA L. Журнал химии товаров и народной медицины, 1(4), 117–133. <https://doi.org/10.55475/jcgtm/vol1.iss4.2022.76>
33. Самадов, Б. Ш., Джалилов, Ф. С., Юлдашева, Д. Х., Джалилова, Ф. С., Болтаев, М. М., & Мелибоева, Ш. Ш. к. (2022). ХИМИЧЕСКИЙ СОСТАВ ЛЕКАРСТВЕННОГО РАСТЕНИЯ МОМОРДИКА CHARANTIA L, ПРИМЕНЯЕМОГО В НАРОДНОЙ МЕДИЦИНЕ. Журнал химии

товаров и народной медицины, 1(4), 134-161.
<https://doi.org/10.55475/jcgtm/vol1.iss4.2022.86>

34. Samadov, B. S., Jalilova, F. S., & Jalilov, F. S. (2022). PROSPECTS FOR OBTAINING DOSAGE FORMS BASED ON MOMORDICA CHARANTIA L. *Scientific progress*, 3(8), 29-32.

35. Samadov, B. S., Jalilova, F. S., & Jalilov, F. S. (2022). PROSPECTS FOR OBTAINING DOSAGE FORMS BASED ON LOCALIZED INDIAN POMEGRANATE. *Scientific progress*, 3(8), 33-41.

36. Громов Иван Александрович, Баранник В. А., Торшхоева Р. М., Намазова Л. С. Применение поливитаминов у детей // ПФ. 2007. №6.

37. Samadov, B. S., Jalilova, F. S., & Jalilov, F. S. (2022). ANALYSIS OF THE COMPONENTS OF THE COLLECTION OF MEDICINAL PLANT RAW MATERIALS OF MOMORDICA CHARANTIA L. *Scientific progress*, 3(8), 49-57.

38. Samadov, B. S., Zhalilov, F. S., & Zhalilova, F. S. (2022). HYPOLIPIDEMIC ACTIVITY OF THE MEDICINAL PLANT MOMORDICA HARANTIA. *Medical Scientific Bulletin of Central Chernozemye (Naučno-medicinskij vestnik Central'nogo Ćernozem'â)*, (89), 57-69.

39. Самадов, Б. Ш., Джалилов, Ф. С., & Джалилова, Ф. С. (2022). АНАТОМИЧЕСКОЕ СТРОЕНИЕ ЛЕКАРСТВЕННОГО РАСТЕНИЯ MOMORDICA CHARANTIA L. *Журнал химии*

товаров и народной медицины, 1(5), 123-149.
<https://doi.org/10.55475/jcgtm/vol1.iss5.2022.109>